

TIMED KEY:

Adding Time to A Password

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Abstract:

This method is intended to improve security in the cyberspace by adding an extra layer of security that works as the very last resource in order to protect and, more practically, recover control back after there is harm from an external attack to a said cyber system. Method has two (2) form / ways of being applied / integrated to current technology. Method is very useful on software updates, amongst other situations.

I coded in old Pascal a sample application for Windows in which method proves is practicality and functionality. You can find code in the following link:

<https://github.com/bilbut/Timed-Key>

I. DETAILS

A. Introduction:

- This method was designed for the authentication time but can be used in other ways such as to decrypt o encrypt a message at a specific time (with a specific date and time in mind). This time factor would work as a secondary key / password.
- When I mention "Authentication Time," I mean when a user or system is logging into another system.

B. What problem does this method solve?

- My method is very useful for scheduled authentications: automated authentications / logins.
- The first thing that comes to my mind when there is mentioned automated authentications are scheduled updates.
- As you can infer, system updates are very common to update software such as apps and operative systems.
- My method is not a layer of security itself, at least I see it that way.
- *I prefer to see this method as an improvement to current layers of security.*

C. Possible situation in which method can be useful:

- A group of people, somehow and successfully, put in place a false update to an operative system that has many active users.
- Because of time resources, this group of people launch the false update as soon as they can access to this option / goal.
- With my method in place, this update would not launch because of the time factor, which in this case behaves as a second password.
- Only updates launched at a specified and agreed time between users' device and system would proceed successfully.

D. Proof of concept:

- Please find in the folder containing this project a Practical Demo that proves concept.
- Step one (1): Set up a password and also set when the time of the password.
 - o A hash is generated after clicking "SET."
 - o This hash is the one used as the password (when using your favorite encryption method).
- Step two (2): All modern systems are based on time, amongst many other factors, but I mean that all of them count on time.
 - o In a real situation, time does not need to be set in step two because time is the actual time of the system.
 - System can be users' device or a system itself, depending on the use / situation being addressed.
 - o Please set a time when system receives request for authentication and click "SET."
- Step three (3): Try to access system by clicking "ACCESS SYSTEM."
 - o If both times previously agreed coincide, then access would be granted.
 - o However, if times are different, then there would not be access and result would be an authentication error.
 - o Of course, in a real situation, password must also be the correct one, which is a little weird to say because password and time behave as one itself as you will see in the following pages. That's why I refer to this type of password as "timed password."
- I leave you the function I coded in old Pascal. In project folder is also the source code of the practical demo, which contains the following function.
 - o Function puts into practice all steps of method found in the following pages.

```
function Submit(source : String; extact_date : TDateTime) : String;
// By: Carlos Guzman
// Date: 05/29/2020
// Req. Classes: DateUtils
// Call: Submit (String, Time in Unix);
// Use: Generate hash from string
// based on time.
var
  Time_Unix : Int64;
  i, q : Integer;
  Ix, t : Int64;
  sort : TStringList;
  m, n: Double;
  s : String;
begin
  Time_Unix := DateTimeToUnix(extact_date);
  sort := TStringList.Create;

  for i := 1 to Length(source) do begin
    t := 1;

    if (i+1) <= Length(source) then begin
      for q := (i+1) to (Length(source)) do begin
        t := t * Ord(source[q]) * q;
      end;
    end;
    t := t * Ord(source[i]) * (Time_Unix - i);
```

```
RandSeed := t;  
Ix := Random(t);  
  
RandSeed := Ix;  
for q := 1 to 10 do begin  
  sort.Add(IntToStr(Random(Ix)));  
end;  
sort.CustomSort(MySortProc);  
  
m := StrToInt64(sort[4]);  
n := StrToInt64(sort[0]);  
  
s := s + FloatToStr(Abs(m * n));  
  
sort.Clear;  
end;  
sort.Free;  
Result := s;  
end;  
  
function MySortProc(List: TStringList; Index1, Index2: Integer): Integer;  
var  
  Value1, Value2: Integer;  
begin  
  Value1 := StrToInt(List[Index1]);  
  Value2 := StrToInt(List[Index2]);  
  
  if Value1 < Value2 then  
    Result := -1  
  else if Value2 < Value1 then  
    Result := 1  
  else  
    Result := 0;  
end;
```

E. What happens in cases in which there is a time delay or bulk update and system is not able to receive and/or send request at the specified time?

- In these cases, a relative time is needed.
- Example of an update situation:
 - o User's device has set to receive update on 06/01/2020 at 12:00 AM.
 - o However, user's device received the update request on 06/01/2020 at 12:07 AM.
- Set user's device to have the flexibility to receive a valid update the entire day of 06/01/2020.
 - o Updates outside that day (24 hours) are invalid even if timed password is valid.
- During 06/01/2020, user's device receives the update request at 12:07 AM.
 - o There are many ways of negotiating a password, but let's suppose that both user's device and system sending request (simply "system") use Diffie-Hellman Key Exchange Method to negotiate a password.
 - o System creates a timed password set for 06/01/2020 at 12:00 AM using the password from the negotiation.
 - o User's device does the same and create a timed password.
 - o Then, authentication takes place either by:
 - Sending/receiving valid data right away after timed password synchronization (Not recommended).

- Generating a hash using timed password and see if hashes from system and user's device coincide.
- (Recommended) Generate hashes and see if they coincide. If they do coincide, encrypt using timed password and start sending data then.
- In other words, time of update is a sensitive data.

F. Quick Notes:

- Above description of a possible solution to a real problem can be tempting to be used as the official way of doing this method.
- However, I designed this method to use time as a sudden (last minute) factor of security.
- I say that if time is going to be used as a "secondary password," please take necessary security steps to keep this piece of information (precise time) safe.

G. How to use time as a sudden security factor (Example)?

- Following the same example above but with a small change:
 - System is going to send an update request to only one (1) user's device.
- Update is scheduled to 06/01/2020 at 12:00 AM.
- User's device receives System's request at 12:00:00 AM that day (exact date and time).
- Password is timed and then authentication takes place same way as above example.
- There is not flexibility in this case.

H. Other uses to this method:

- (Online) Internal tasks such as authentication and/or simply encrypt/decrypt in both System and Users' devices (sudden factor).
- (Offline) To encrypt and decrypt messages offline (secondary password).
- Relative Time (bulk updates with time delays)

I. What improvements does this method add when under attack?

- As I have explained before, a timed password is not only a password because it is a password plus time.
- Due to the fact that this method is just an improvement, let's suppose that password is compromised but not time.
- Situation here is that a message is under attack (but it could easily be attacking to authenticate by using brute force).
 - Password is compromised.
 - Time is unknown.
 - Encrypted message is known.
 - Encryption method is known.
 - Attackers have cyber tools to decrypt encrypted message.
- To the surprise of attackers, password does not work and they are sure that they have arrived to the right password after the brute force attack or any other method used.
- What's next? Finding time.

J. What are the possibilities of finding time?

From the definition of Unix Time [1], software [2] can be created in order to help us better calculate the exact Unix Time we are looking for.

Method takes into account (Unix):

- Year
 - Month
 - Day
 - Hour
 - Minute
 - Second
- Let's suppose that attackers have even more data such as:

Accuracy of Attackers' Information	How many possibilities are out there?
Time to the minute (attackers know year, month, day, hour and minute)	1/60
Time to the hour (attackers know year, month, day, hour)	1/3600
Time to the day (attackers know year, month, day)	1/86400
Time to the week (attackers know year, month, week)	1/604800
Time to the month (attackers know year, month)	1/(2.628*10 ⁶)
Time to the year (attackers know year)	1/(3.154*10 ⁷)
Total Brute Force	1/(1591050672) = 1/(1.59*10 ⁹) (up to 06/01/2020)

- Of course, encryption method has to be secure such as a modern one.
- As you can see, when talking about possibilities, this method is weak (not to say extremely weak).
- However, purpose of this method is to have a sudden impact (very last layer of security) and, upon a wrong authentication, take necessary security steps such as:
 - Notify of the breach:
 - Based on the numbers in the table, there would not be any time to prevent anything (manual) unless automatic steps are taken.
 - Using modern computers, cracking down method using a 100% brute force attack would take minutes to say much.
 - Please keep in mind that upon frequent updates, it is very possible that at least year, month and perhaps the day are going to be obvious for attackers. I mean, attackers will try to get the shortcut by using obviousness.
 - Take steps to restore safety.
 - This is, automatic steps such as denying all incoming update requests for the day.
 - Set scheduled update time for the following day.
 - Manual actions (time is again sensitive here) to figure out from where the attack came from and restore the safety of users and system as soon as possible.
 - Most probably fact is that manual actions are to be taken after breach, cracking down of system, automatic steps taken by

Now we multiply X_1 and X_4

Result is $X_1 * X_4$

Result for P (first letter of password) = $200003322 * 1203337878$

Next step is to do the same for each of the letters of password.

Resulting hash will be:

Hash = Result(P) + Result(A) + Result(S) + Result(S) + Result(W) + Result(O) + Result(R) + Result(D)

Please note that above operation to generate hash is not addition. For example:

Result for M = 15

Result for N = 23

Hash = Result(M) + Result (N) = 1523

III. CONCLUSION

- Hash generated varies enormously even when making a small change:
 - o From Practical Demo (GitHub Project).

Date & Time: June 15, 2020 13:30:00

Key: PASSWORD

Result:

9944309472434601.92490329262371E1612829613530029617409145900296.6773668865413
7E163.61487652694448E162805696190541042.48450920364834E15

Date & Time: June 15, 2020 13:30:01

Key: PASSWORD

Result:

9.05460196823854E166.83790568179929E162.02709055331241E152.11181829508738E153.
57959474272931E161.34011257423027E181942601410089271.44257693008369E15

Date & Time: June 15, 2020 13:31:00

Key: PASSWORD

Result:

5.9527847647797E161.07413271302295E154.83890407422145E153.8438306305637E15409
0315514933043.7921405578797E15358512361898075223647455048352

Date & Time: June 15, 2021 13:30:00

Key: PASSWORD

Result:

5.17429732606014E151.70701314806825E162.01713735430266E155.96819579412527E162.
7649204658819E155.23865336121861E167637554939305069.41992537257156E16

Date & Time: January 1, 1980 17:30:00

Key: PASSWORD

Result:

5.57853232240805E158.01492423081416E164.2003437128328E167.77061877574633E152.7
2444370820178E152042022956421938.04783843631841E177.40957536299471E17

Date & Time: June 15, 2020 13:30:00

Key: SSSS

Result:

2.05540093431317E155.26603752797857E161.09097172234617E171.49255827041934E16

Date & Time: June 15, 2020 13:30:00

Key: SSSSS

Result:

1.13677125976591E161.55320142573282E165.1661406925041E161.14578395881333E1751
7038018620760

IV. FINAL NOTES

Please remember that after generating hash, use your favorite modern encryption as usual.

Of course, results should not contain letter E as above example because it means 10 to the power of.

- I used it because old Pascal has a relatively low limits on the variables' values.

So, this is basically the Timed Key Method.

Thanks for reading!

REFERENCES

[1] En.wikipedia.org. 2020. *Unix Time*. [online] Available at: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unix_time>

[2] Unixtimestamp.com. 2020. *Unix Time Stamp - Epoch Converter*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.unixtimestamp.com/index.php>>